

CS-SDG

Data Management Plan

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Abstract	The Data Management Plan outlines the details and procedures for how to handle data generated in the project according to the relevant aspects of making data FAIR, including which data the project will generate, whether and how it will be made accessible for verification and reuse, and how it will be curated and preserved.
Keywords	Citizen Science, Conference, Sustainable Development Goals, SDGs, Data management, DMP

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1. Version Log

Version	Date	Released by	Nature of Change
1.0	28/04/2020	Claudia Fabó Cartas (MfN)	Initial draft for discussion within the CS-SDG project team
1.1	29/04/2020	Claudia Fabó Cartas (MfN)	Final Review CS-SDG project team

2. Definitions and Acronyms

CC	Creative Commons
CORDIS	Community Research and Development Information Service. It is the European Commission's primary public repository and portal to disseminate information on all EU-funded research projects and their results.
Data	“Information, in particular facts or numbers, collected to be examined and considered as a basis for reasoning, discussion, or calculation. In a research context, examples of data include statistics, results of experiments, measurements, observations resulting from fieldwork, survey results, interview recordings and images. The focus is on research data that is available in digital form” (European Commission, 2016b).
DMP	Data Management Plan
EC	European Commission
ECSA	European Citizen Science Association
Ecsite	European network of science centres and museums
EU-Citizen.Science	European citizen science platform
ERA	European Research Area
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable
GA	Grant Agreement

GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
H2020	Horizon 2020
ID	Identification
MfN	Museum für Naturkunde Berlin
Open Access	Access that is free to all and free of any restrictions
ORD	Open Research Data
RRI	Responsible Research and Innovation
SDGs	Sustainable Development Goals
SwafS	Science with and for Society
WP	Working Package

3. Executive Summary

The CS-SDG Data Management Plan (DMP) is Deliverable 6.1 (D6.1), part of work package 6 “Project Management” from project CS-SDG, grant agreement (GA) No. 101000014. This deliverable introduces the DMP for the project.

The Data Management Plan describes the details and procedures for handling data collected or generated in the project according to the relevant aspects of making data FAIR (findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable), including what data the project will generate, if and how it will be made available and how it will be curated and preserved.

The aim of this document is to lay out the DMP for the project. The purpose of the document is to put in place the definitions, explanations and details that will facilitate the potential reuse of the data that will be collected during the project. The DMP will allow this data to be in accordance with the Horizon 2020 Open Research Data pilot.

This report deals with the following issues:

- 1) How CS-SDG will manage data collected or generated in the project
- 2) How data will be made findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable

4. Introduction

The Data Management Plan (DMP) for the CS-SDG project will set out the details and definitions that will enable the potential reuse of the data collected and processed in the project. The DMP will ensure that this data will be findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable (FAIR), in line with the Horizon 2020 Open Research Data pilot.

4.1. Project background

The CS-SDG project is supported by the European Commission under its Horizon 2020 programme Science with and for Society (SwafS). The project will lead to the organisation of a citizen science conference which will bring together and showcase impactful citizen science initiatives, provide policy input to ongoing European developments and inspire the upcoming ten years of citizen science initiatives. CS-SDG will address this challenge by focusing on citizen science as a relevant approach to contributing to Global Challenges and industrial competitiveness in Horizon Europe, to the UN’s Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and to building upon ongoing initiatives in the Open Science strategy, the European Research Area (ERA) and Horizon 2020. The “Knowledge for Change – A decade of citizen science (2020-2030) in support of the SDGs” conference will represent a crucial opportunity to bring together lessons learnt from initiatives at global, national, regional and grassroots level, to scale up their impacts, address existing challenges and harness the potential of citizen science towards achieving the SDGs. One of the main conference outcomes will be a declaration with recommendations, gathering input in a collaborative way from conference participants and selected experts, focusing on the future of citizen science and its implementation in future funding programmes.

CS-SDG will organise a conference gathering policy-makers and citizen science projects – from all parts of the world, from local to global scales, and both community-led and academic-led – to build the future of citizen science policymaking. The conference will be an opportunity to showcase the diversity of citizen science projects, and a forum for reflection and perspective, with transversal sessions to define together the latest developments, impacts, benefits and challenges of citizen science, as well as a global Citizen Science Festival. Most importantly, collaborative sessions will draw recommendations to feed in strategic policy recommendations for the decade 2020-2030.

In brief, the conference will comprise:

- months of engagement with projects and policy-makers before the conference
- a Festival to showcase the diversity of citizen science projects in terms of approach, theme and geographic area
- sessions to examine some prominent projects in detail, especially their relationship to the SDGs
- sessions to draw a ‘state of the art’ of citizen science for policy-makers
- collaborative sessions to build strategic policy recommendations at the European level for the next decade

The conference will take place during the German Presidency of the Council of the European Union from 14-15 October 2020 in Berlin.

The project work plan is distributed over six work packages (WP).

WP1 Conference Organisation

The overall aim of this WP is to take care of the organisational and logistical aspects of the CS-SDG conference, which will take place in Berlin on 14 and 15 October 2020. Specific objectives include:

- conference logistics: venue, catering and other external services

- set-up and management of the Conference Programme Committee
- conference programme

WP2 Policy and Strategy

The main tasks in this WP are:

- To frame the collaborative process to build the policy recommendations and choose an appropriate participatory methodology. This task includes the liaison with the EC in developing a strong link between citizen science and the Open Science strategy, the European Research Area (ERA), Horizon 2020 and Horizon Europe, which will ultimately lead to the production of concrete recommendations.
- To strategically engage with European policy-makers, with the aim of exploring the role of the member states and the connections between European, national, international and local policy dimensions and levels of citizen engagement through conference sessions. Liaise with the EC and other international policy-makers in developing a strong link between citizen science and SDGs, showcasing how citizen science projects address key issues in achieving the SDGs and generate empowerment towards shared solutions.
- To run collaborative sessions to build the policy-recommendations, and synthesise them in a common conference declaration.

WP3 Collaboration and networking

WP3 is dedicated to bringing together and taking stock of the current and past citizen science projects in Europe and beyond. The aim of this WP is to map and connect with these projects (in collaboration with the EU-Citizen.Science project) as well as to identify the current trends and challenges which will result in defining the main areas of the conference. Special attention will be paid to make sure that non-European citizen science initiatives are also present: the facilitation will have a specific attention to inclusion of all voices.

One of the main outcomes of WP3 will be the citizen science festival. The festival will be a designated area of the conference where past and existing citizen science projects will have stands where they will be able to showcase their results, findings and processes. The festival will be open to projects at all scales and from anywhere in the world. Projects showcasing at the festival will be chosen through a contest and according to previously defined selection criteria, in line with the key priorities of the conference. MfN will organise the citizen science festival in close cooperation with WiD (Wissenschaft im Dialog, Berlin) and select invited international projects.

WP4 Evaluation

This WP focuses on the conference evaluation which will be performed by an external evaluator, under the guidance of MfN, through a methodological approach based on both qualitative and quantitative methods. The conference evaluation will collect valuable feedback, not only about the quality of the conference, but also conducting an impact assessment which will contribute to the production of useful outcomes for the advancement of citizen science support and diffusion.

WP5 Communication and outreach

The main task of this WP is to make sure that the wider citizen science community, policy-makers (EU and national level), researchers, citizen scientists, and civil society organisations are informed of the conference and its outcomes. This will be done through active liaison with existing citizen science projects, social media, relevant networks such as ECSA, Ecsite, EU-Citizen.Science, as well as national citizen science networks, H2020 national contact points, European Commission channels, advertising in journals or magazines, etc. This task will also ensure the conference's online presence. Special attention will be paid to ensure that an online archive of the conference sessions is available, and speakers will be asked to upload a documentation for their session i.e. powerpoint presentations, written contributions, videos.

WP6 Project Management

This WP focuses on project management tasks, including financial and project reporting and reporting to the EC.

4.2. Data Management Plan Objectives

This document is an initial Data Management Plan (DMP) for the CS-SDG project. The DMP outlines the details and procedures for how to handle data collected and generated in the project according to the relevant aspects of making data FAIR (findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable), including what data the project will generate, whether and how it will be made accessible for verification and reuse, and how it will be curated and preserved.

The project itself aims to organise a conference gathering policy-makers and citizen science projects – from all parts of the world, from local to global scales, and both community-led and academic-led – to build the future of citizen science policymaking. This means that a big portion of the data being handled within the project is personal data.

In accordance with Guidelines on FAIR Data management in Horizon 2020 (European Commission, 2016a), the objectives of the DMP are:

- To identify the data that the CS-SDG project will produce;
- To define how the data will be made 'FAIR' (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable);
- To define the allocation of resources (costs and responsibility) for data management during and after the project;
- To define procedures for data security (including data recovery as well as safe storage) during the project and for long-term preservation.

The Deliverable 6.1 "Data management plan" is part of work package 6 "Project Management", and has been developed following the Horizon 2020 guidelines, with additional guidelines from DMPonline as suggested by the European Commission.

As a key element of sustainable data management, the DMP describes what and how data will be collected, processed and/or generated, which methodology and standards will be applied, whether data will be shared/made open access, and also how data will be curated and preserved during the project and afterwards. It provides guidelines, answers to issues, and presents the approach that the CS-SDG project will adopt with respect to the management and protection of data. Legal and ethical issues related to the project's collecting and/or processing of personal data are identified in relation to data protection, taking into consideration the different methods by which data are collected (interview, online survey, workshop, questionnaire etc.).

An updated version of the Data Management Plan will be released when other types of data are generated/collected, when changes in project policies, and whenever any other external factors affect the validity of the present DMP.

All activities, procedures and instruments of data collection, processing and storage comply with the protection of personal data and intellectual property rights of the European Union, as defined by the European Commission. CS-SDG will not collect sensitive personal data. Furthermore, none of the participants' names or affiliations will be included in the project deliverables and dissemination materials without prior informed consent. We plan to engage citizens and quadruple helix stakeholders to participate actively in conference activities. Informed consent will be sought for all participants, also for the production of dissemination outcomes such as videos and the photo gallery. The CS-SDG project will ensure the long-term preservation of the data (omitting personal data).

5. Project Data

5.1. State the purpose of the data collection

The purpose of the data collection is, on the one hand, to coordinate organisational and logistical aspects of the CS-SDG conference, which will take place in Berlin on 14 and 15 October 2020, and, on the other hand, to develop the conference declaration and to evaluate the quality as well as impact of the conference.

5.2. Explain the relation to the objectives of the project

The CS-SDG project will organise a conference that will present, evaluate and discuss the exciting contributions that citizen science makes in framing and achieving sustainable development, specifically the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). Established and emerging instruments for sustainability in citizen science will be discussed and it will bring together expertise from politicians, institutional and citizen scientists, economists, NGOs and civil society to implement mechanisms and processes for the transition towards a more sustainable future. One of the main conference outcomes will be a declaration with recommendations, gathering input in a collaborative way from conference participants and selected experts focusing on the future of citizen science and its implementation in future funding programmes.

The data collection is required in order to carry out the following tasks:

- to coordinate organisational and logistical aspects of the CS-SDG conference
- to coordinate organisational and logistical aspects of the Citizen Science Festival
- to gather input in a collaborative way from conference participants and selected experts, focusing on the future of citizen science as well as its implementation in future funding programmes and to synthesise them in a joint conference declaration
- to evaluate the impact and quality of the conference, which will help to produce useful outcomes for the promotion and dissemination of Citizen Science

5.3. Specify the types and formats of data generated/collected

Type of data:

- Personal data
 - Name
 - Affiliation
 - Country
 - Mailing address
 - Phone number (optional)
 - Professional background (optional)
 - (Job) title
 - Gender (female, male, I do not want to specify)

- Other data
 - Data from signing-up to attend the conference
 - Data from signing-up to present at the conference
 - Data from submitted applications from projects to be invited to the Festival
 - Data from input given by conference participants on the future of citizen science and its implementation in future funding programmes to develop the conference declaration. In detail, these inputs are: statements of expectations, comments of interest and experience reports.
 - Data from selected expert interviews with active researchers, multipliers and policy-makers with which further information for a successful formulation of the declaration are generated. These are supporting statements, estimates and references.
 - Data from the documentation of the discussion and deliberation process related to the declaration
 - Data from an (online) survey to get feedback from a maximum of participants on various sessions, features and conference aspects to evaluate the impact and assess the quality of the conference (in cooperation with a commissioned, external evaluator)
 - Data from semi-structured interviews with selected participants from all quadruple helix stakeholder groups for the evaluation of the conference (in cooperation with a commissioned, external evaluator)
 - Scientific papers (emerging from conference proposals submissions), published in a special issue of the peer-reviewed journal "Sustainability" on "Citizen Science and the Role in Sustainable Development"

Formats of the data:

To facilitate data exchange, MS Excel compatible files including comma separated and .xls(x) format will be used. Documents such as scientific papers as well as documents built through collaborative sessions such as the conference declaration will be stored in MS Word compatible files or in PDF files.

5.4. Specify if existing data is being reused

No existing data is being reused.

5.5. Specify the origin of the data**Origin of the data:**

- Data from signing-up to attend the conference
- Data from signing-up to present at the conference
- Data from submitted applications from projects to be invited to the Festival
- Data from input given by conference participants on the future of citizen science and its implementation in future funding programmes to develop the conference declaration. In detail, these inputs are: statements of expectations, comments of interest and experience reports.
- Data from selected expert interviews with active researchers, multipliers and policy-makers with which further information for a successful formulation of the declaration are generated. These are supporting statements, estimates and references.
- Data from the documentation of the discussion and deliberation process related to the declaration
- Data from an (online) survey to get feedback from a maximum of participants on various sessions, features and conference aspects to evaluate the impact and assess the quality of the conference (in cooperation with a commissioned, external evaluator)
- Data from semi-structured interviews with selected participants from all quadruple helix stakeholder groups for the evaluation of the conference (in cooperation with a commissioned, external evaluator)
- Scientific papers (emerging from conference proposals submissions), published in a special issue of the peer-reviewed journal "Sustainability" on "Citizen Science and the Role in Sustainable Development"

5.6. State the expected size of the data

To be evaluated during the course of the project. The expected size depends on the extent and the nature of the data that are made available.

5.7. Outline the data utility: to whom will it be useful

The above-mentioned data could be useful to the CS-SDG project, the services of the European Commission and the European Community of Citizen Science, as well as stakeholder groups identified in the proposal (policy-makers, researchers, citizens etc.).

6. FAIR Data

This section is written using the standard H2020 template for FAIR data given in the Guidelines on FAIR Data management in Horizon 2020 (European Commission, 2016a).

6.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

6.1.1. Outline naming conventions used

Project deliverables are assigned a unique identifier CS-SDG_[number of Deliverable]_[date of submission], e.g. CS-SDG_D5.1_31032020 (already submitted).

All files made publicly available (omitting scientific papers) reference CS-SDG in their name, with the recommendation that files be named [meaningful short description of the file] CS-SDG or [meaningful short description of the file] CS SDG Conference.

6.1.2. Outline the approach towards search keyword

We provide search keywords in project deliverables for optimising possibilities for reuse.

6.1.3. Outline the approach for clear versioning

Deliverable reports will have a data identification sheet and version log.

6.2. Making data openly accessible

6.2.1. Specify which data will be made openly available

Personal data (e.g. personal data submitted for participation in the conference) will not be disclosed or made available to third parties to ensure the privacy of conference and festival participants. Personal data processed within the project will be stored until the end of the project in January 2021 and deleted afterwards.

Personal data of members from citizen science projects who have been invited to showcase their projects at the Festival will neither be disclosed nor made available to third parties, but the names of the invited projects will be published on the conference website.

The name and affiliation of speakers at the conference and their abstracts submitted through the call for contributions to conference sessions, will be published on the conference website. Non-selected abstracts will not be made publicly available.

The declaration and all data used for its formulation will be made publicly available as an online living document. Data from input given by conference participants and selected experts will be

anonymised. A documentation of the discussion and deliberation process related to the declaration will be provided in a summary form. The conference declaration will be published publicly in the form of a delivery (D2.1).

Data from online surveys and interviews will not be made publicly available as Open Research Data (ORD). They will be securely stored by CS-SDG project members. The evaluation report will be published publicly in the form of a delivery (D4.1).

Scientific papers (resulting from the conference proposals) can be published in a special issue on "Citizen Science and the Role in Sustainable Development" in the peer-reviewed journal "Sustainability".

6.2.2. Specify how the data will be made available

During the project, a subset of summary data (e.g. conference participant and festival visitor statistics and feedback summaries) will be made available by one or more methods below:

- via newsletters, reports and other publications on the conference website
- via partner's local websites
- via social media

Data that will be made available through the conference website are:

- names and affiliations of speakers at the conference as well as their abstracts submitted through the call for contributions to conference sessions
- names of invited projects at the festival
- the conference declaration
- results of the conference evaluation

The conference declaration as well as the evaluation report will be publicly published in the form of deliverables (D2.1 und D4.1 respectively).

At the end of the project, data to be preserved will be stored as resources on the EU-Citizen.Science platform.

6.2.3. Specify what methods or software tools are needed to access the data

Data will be published using standard file formats (.doc(x), .xls(x), .txt, .pdf, etc.). All data will be accessible using standard tools.

6.2.4. Specify where the data and associated metadata, documentation and code are deposited

For the duration of the project, personal data will be stored on MfN's secured servers. Data to be public are stored on a central drive.

6.2.5. Specify how access will be provided in case there are any restrictions

At this stage, no restrictions are envisaged; should it be required, the appropriate open software will be provided to access the data or export the data to standard formats.

6.3. Making data interoperable**6.3.1. Assess the interoperability of your data. Specify what data and metadata vocabularies, standards or methodologies you will follow to facilitate interoperability**

In the CS-SDG project, we use standard file formats as noted above. The project will be using standard vocabularies for all data types present in the project's data set, to facilitate interoperability.

6.3.2. Specify whether you will be using standard vocabulary for all data types present in your data set, to allow inter-disciplinary interoperability? If not, will you provide mapping to more commonly used ontologies?

The project will be using standard vocabularies for all data types present in the project's data set, to allow inter-disciplinary interoperability.

6.4. Making data reusable**6.4.1. Specify how the data will be licenced to permit the widest reuse possible**

It is planned that CC Licenses will be used for all data to be preserved.

6.4.2. Specify when the data will be made available for reuse. If applicable, specify why and for what period a data embargo is needed

It is not envisaged that the project will seek patents. The data collected and analysed during the project (omitting personal data) will be made openly available at the end of the project at the latest.

6.4.3. Specify whether the data produced and/or used in the project is usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project? If the reuse of some data is restricted, explain why

All personal data will be restricted to internal usage and will neither be made publicly accessible nor available to third parties. For openly available information, standard format, open source software (if required), and proper documentation will guarantee reusability by third parties.

6.4.4. Specify the length of time for which the data will remain reusable

Personal data of conference participants will all be deleted at the end of the conference. Data such as abstracts, powerpoint slides, recordings of lectures relevant to the Citizen Science community as well as to Citizen Science Policy will be stored long-term on EU-Citizen.Science. The EU-Citizen.Science platform will host all important outcomes from the conference, and make sure these are widely disseminated within the citizen science community. Data storage

on the EU-Citizen.Science platform after the end of the CS-SDG project is ensured at least for five years after the end of the EU-Citizen.Science project in December 2021, that is, until December 2026, under the responsibility of ECSA. Therefore, data (omitting personal data) will remain reusable for 6 years.

7. Allocation of resources

7.1. Estimate the costs for making your data FAIR. Describe how you intend to cover these costs

Most of the data that will be made publicly available will be done so through the conference website. The conference website has to be paid for independently of making the project data FAIR. Therefore, there are no additional costs incurred by making the project data FAIR.

Other data will be published in the form of project deliverables openly accessible and ready to download through the CORDIS portal at: <https://cordis.europa.eu/search/en>. There are no additional costs incurred by this.

Copyright licensing with Creative Commons is free of charge.

7.2. Clearly identify responsibilities for data management in your project

Every project member will be responsible for data collected or generated as the result of the activities or tasks for which they are responsible, i.e. the person(s) responsible for the declaration will be responsible for the data produced by formulating the declaration. The Principal Investigator and the Project Manager are co-responsible for general coordination and supervision.

7.3. Describe costs and potential value of long-term preservation

Since the declaration is a living document its content will be preserved and evolve at the same time. The costs of long-term preservation can be ignored since this would occur through already existing citizen science platforms, social media and other channels not created for the sole purpose of long-term preservation of the declaration. Furthermore, the declaration will contain strategic policy recommendations for the decade 2020-2030. Therefore, the preservation of the conference declaration will be sought until at least 2030.

The results of the conference evaluation will be stored for up to 6 years on the EU-Citizen.Science platform and for probably longer on CORDIS in the form of a project deliverable. Costs incurred from long-term preservation of the evaluation report on the EU-Citizen.Science platform and on CORDIS can be ignored since the platform is not created for the sole purpose of long-term preservation of the evaluation report and storage on CORDIS is free of charge. The potential value of storing the results of the conference beyond that date could diminish over time, as the best practices for a conference in 2020 may be outdated ten years later.

The value of long-term storage of other data, if any, is low.

8. Data security

The EU-Citizen.Science project will ensure that any personal data collected throughout the activities of the project will be protected in a safe and secure way, in full compliance with GDPR requirements, assuring privacy requirements and preventing improper use. Personal data (e.g. personal data submitted for attendance to the conference) will not be made openly accessible, nor available to third parties to guarantee conference and festival participants' privacy. Personal data processed in the project will be stored until the end of the project in January 2021 and deleted afterwards.

The following procedures will be included in the project protocol to safeguard the privacy of participants:

- Reported project results will pertain to analyses of data. No individual's name will be associated with any published or unpublished report of the conference;
- Personal information, including questionnaires, will be safely stored locally in secure facilities, and names will be replaced by unique numbers (ID codes) stored separately. Primary data files will be stored on computers with personal identifiers removed.
- ID codes will link all basic data required for the project and will be stored in password protected computer files. Access to these files will be limited to authorised project personnel.
- In the case that participants will provide their contact details (phone number, e-mail address) after having given their consent to participating and having agreed to being re-contacted for research purposes, this information will be stored in password protected computer files. Access to these files will be limited to authorised project personnel, whose names will be communicated to participants.
- Hard copy records or computer-generated records containing personally identifiable information will be stored in locked cabinets in an office with limited access and shredded at the end of the project.
- The project personnel will be informed of the importance of confidentiality of individual records and required to sign a confidentiality agreement.
- Project members have to carefully consider all challenges for data storage, including deleting all data no longer required for the project, or at the request of the owner of that data. Project members are therefore obliged to periodically review the data they hold and erase or anonymise it when no longer needed.
- During the project data will be regularly backed-up.

9. Ethical aspects

The MfN is aware of the following guidance and codes, which will be considered during the project execution:

- Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union;
- European Convention on Human Rights and its Supplementary Protocols;

- Regulation (EU) 2016/679 (GDPR) on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data;
- The New Brunswick Declaration: A Declaration on Research Ethics, Integrity and Governance resulting from the 1st Ethics Rupture Summit, Fredericton, New Brunswick, Canada (2013);
- The Respect Code focused in socio-economic research (<http://www.respectproject.org>)
- The Code of Ethics of the International Sociological Association (<http://www.isasociology.org/en/about-isa/code-of-ethics/>);
- The European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity, Revised Edition, by ALLEA - All European Academies 2017;
- The ten principles of Citizen Science of the European Citizen Science Association (https://ecsa.citizen-science.net/sites/default/files/ecsa_ten_principles_of_citizen_science.pdf)

We have reviewed the guidance available on the web¹ and are aware of RRI guidelines, and the Collection of Citizen Science guidelines and publications that will be consulted throughout the project.²

The ethics issues identified for implementing the actions of the CS-SDG project and how they will be dealt with are summarised below.

- **Consent to the collection and processing of data** by the MfN will be collected before conference and festival participants submit any data.
- **Informed consent procedures:** We plan to engage citizens and quadruple helix stakeholders to participate actively in conference activities. Informed consent will be sought for all participants, also for the production of dissemination outcomes such as videos and the photo gallery.
- **Participation in the project may involve persons unable to give informed consent:** The participation of children/minors is not foreseen. All conference participants will be at least 18 years old.
- **Data management:** All issues related to data management are described in detail in this DMP.

10. Conclusion

The DMP for the CS-SDG project outlines the details and procedures for how to handle data generated in the project according to the relevant aspects of making data FAIR (findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable), including which data the project will generate, whether and how it will be made accessible for verification and reuse, and how it will be curated and preserved. A big portion of the data being handled within the project is personal data. The DMP addresses the way in which personal data must be handled.

¹ <http://ec.europa.eu/research/swafs/index.cfm?pg=policy&lib=ethics> [last accessed April 28th 2020]

² <https://ecsa.citizen-science.net/blog/collection-citizen-science-guidelines-and-publications> [last accessed April 28th 2020]

11. References

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